

Enhancing Energy Access in Malawi through Off-grid and Grid Integrated Renewables

Country: **Malawi**

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BACKGROUND

Energy System Sources in Malawi

- Malawi faces low access (35-40%) and unreliable grid electricity issues despite vast potential in solar and biomass.
- Reliance on traditional biomass for domestical use has resulted in pollution and deforestation.
- According to Malawi National Electrification Strategy & Action Plan, we plan to achieve over 60 % access to electricity by 2030 through grid expansion and mini-grids [1]
- The report investigates the potential of off-grid and grid integrated renewable energy systems in increasing clean and equitable energy access.

Research Questions

What is the techno-economic potential of off-grid standalone systems in enhancing energy access in Malawi?

How can renewable energy integration into the main grid contribute to meeting future electricity demand?

What are the most cost-effective and sustainable pathways for Malawi's energy mix inline with National Energy Policy (2018) and universal energy access[2]?

SCENARIOS AND INTERPRETATION

SCENARIO TITLE	DESCRIPTION	KEY ASSUMPTIONS
Baseline Scenario (BAU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maintenance of the current installed capacities with minimal intervention and free flow. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business as usual with the model freely optimizing the system on top of the maintained installed capacities
Access Demand Increase Scenario (ADI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increasing access to electricity to 60% by 2030 according to Malawi National Electrification Strategy & Action Plan using current mix [4] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electricity Energy demand to be used as an indicator to access-RES Current mix potentially capable of meeting the demand.
Off-grid Scale-up Scenario (OGS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scaling-Up Off-Grid access to meet the growing demand in-line with Malawi Renewable Energy Strategy (2017) and Regulatory Framework for Mini-grids at least >50 operational MG by 2025 [3]. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The vast solar potential in Malawi estimated at a daily average of 4.2kWh/m² capable of meeting the demand [5]. Traditional Biomass replaced with low to no emissions

RESULTS

PRODUCTION BY TECHNOLOGY

- Base Scenario showcases current energy trends.
- The Access Demand Increase-Scenario (ADI) doubles demand and freely allows the system to optimize with no constraints.
- Off-Grid Scale-up Scenario (OGS) utilizes the Framework for Mini-grids & the Malawi Renewable Energy Strategy to constrain the system.

ACCUMULATED NEW CAPACITY

Accumulated New Capacity (GW)

INVESTMENT COSTS

ANNUAL TOTAL EMISSION

CONCLUSION AND INSIGHTS

The ADI model is capable of attaining 60% Energy access with minimal emissions and using currently available reserves.

The Off-Grid Scenario comprising of solar and biomass power plants are a real representation of the National Energy Policy to reduce traditional Biomass usage and Increase Off-grid solar and biomass power plants.

The energy sector in Malawi positions itself under the SDG 7 of advocating for Affordable and Clean Energy through targeting zero emission by 2039.

It also aligns with Malawi Agenda 2063 which aims at attaining a diversified energy mix by 2030 and reduce reliance on Hydropower.

References

1. GoM-MNESAP, *Malawi National Electrification Strategy & Action Plan*, M.o. Energy, Editor. 2019
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3. GoM and MERA, Regulatory Framework for Mini-grids. 2019. Accessed: Aug. 12, 2022. [Online]. Available: https://www.energy.gov.mw/wpadmin/adminajax.php?juwpfisadmin=false&action=wpfd&task=file.download&wpfd_category_id=27&wpfd_file_id=1898&token=a28faa1b57dc4bb4ea3057e2622ea075&preview=1
4. Policy, G.-N.E., *Malawi National energy policy*, M.o. Energy, Editor. 2018.
5. Levison,A.K., Nasruddin, Ziba W., 2024: Investigating the Potential of Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV) for Powering Public Buildings in Malawi. <https://theacademic.in/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/38.pdf>

THANK YOU